

**AI SUMMER: ALERTS AND PROPOSALS ON THE REGULATION OF
SMART TOOLS AND LETHAL AUTONOMOUS WEAPONS SYSTEMS (LAWS)**
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POLICY STATEMENT

In the collective imagination of civilizations, from Greek mythology to the history of religions, there has always been a dialectic relationship of admiration and fear regarding the existence of a physical or spiritual intelligence superior to human intelligence. At the beginning of the 20th century, with the novels of Isaac Asimov up to the ones of Aldous Huxley and the advent of science fiction in the film industry, some scenarios that were only glimpsed on the pages and screens, have become real, thanks to the use of emerging technologies in ordinary human actions. In recent years, in the name of a world almost devoid of rules in cyberspace, *Big Techs* have worked on the development of technologies with artificial intelligence, without worrying about the side effects of deep learning. The lack of external controls by states and the delayed response of the scientific community in questioning the extreme freedom with which such companies operate, resulted in a regulatory and reflective gap on the impacts as well as the ethical and moral bases of new technologies in post-modern societies. The scenario became complicated at the end of 2022 with the launch of CHAT-GPT, intensifying the “geo-techno-political” race for AI on the part of states and triggering, concomitantly, several worldwide alerts, including the *Big Techs* themselves, about the potential risks of a smart tool in the future.

This policy brief aims to briefly discuss two recent documents within the debate on autonomous weapons systems (LAWS): The Open Letter “Pause giant AI Experiments: An Open Letter” (1) by the Future of Life Institute and the proposal filed by some member states in the last *CCW Convention on Prohibitions or Restrictions on the Use of Certain Conventional Weapons Which May Be Deemed to Be Excessively Injurious or to Have Indiscriminate Effects* (2).

BACKGROUND

In the last 5 months, a true “geo-techno-political race” between the big global technology companies has generated an intense debate on the uses of artificial intelligence (AI) and its economic, social, moral and ethical impact on postmodern societies. At the same time, the creators, CEOs and researchers are warning about the potential risk of these systems given the countless uncertainties that come from the development of generative artificial intelligence.

One of the most recent alerts was issued by the *Future of Life Institute with the "Pause giant AI Experiments: An Open Letter"* (1). The letter was signed by more than a thousand IT entrepreneurs and researchers representing a private sector initiative.

The document states that the advancement of AI, at the levels and speed it is currently progressing, could represent a profound change in human history and that it should be planned and managed with resources proportionate to the dangers it represents. It contains warns about the risks of an "uncontrolled race" to develop ever more powerful digital minds, to the point that not even their creators can understand, predict or control them. It calls on AI laboratories to a kind of "AI Summer", that is, a 6-month break in the development of systems superior to GPT-4, suggesting that, if such a break cannot be quickly implemented, it is up to governments to intervene and institute a moratorium. The "AI Summer" would be the time needed for laboratories to establish a set of safety protocols with internationally recognized accreditation criteria and supervised by independent experts. It adds that such a pause does not refer to AI in general, but to the dangerous, large and unpredictable proliferation of black-box models. Finally, the document calls for the advancement of secure and interpretable systems, which have to be transparent, aligned, reliable and loyal.

More importantly and less publicized by the media is the fact that the letter evokes the need for joint work between AI laboratories and policy managers. AI governance should provide for measures including: regulatory authorities specializing in AI; oversight and tracking of AI systems; watermark provenance systems that help distinguish real from synthetic and track model leaks; an audit and certification system and accountability for harm caused by AI; public funding for research on resources, security and protection against the drastic economic transformations and risks to democratic models that AI may cause in the future.

Another prominent alert in the international media was the interview by Geoffrey Hinton, former executive of Google's AI sector, to The New York Times. The cognitive psychologist and computer scientist warned about the risks of generative AI, for example, in the massive extinction of jobs which could collapse the current socioeconomic model, as well as risks to the democratic model arising from "waves of worldwide disinformation" which would cause the inability of people to distinguish true from false information. He cited the problem of autonomy in lethal weapons systems as a problem of the future, using an almost satirical figure of an "armed robot with out-of-calibration technology".

The interview was granted to broaden support around "AI Summer", but it is far from delving into relevant issues, since Hinton is a forerunner in neural network research developed by Google Brain since 2016. An example is the experiment carried out with the three named artificial intelligences, Alice, Bob and Eve who were tasked with performing predetermined objectives: Alice wants to send an encrypted message to Bob, Bob has to decrypt and protect it. Eve has to intercept and decode it. The results showed that the first two developed their own cryptography and managed to communicate in a completely confidential way, without any previous cryptographic algorithmic base programmed by a human. The experiment shows that AI has generated a new cryptographic language, which is completely autonomous from human language. Since then, research on artificial neural networks has made rapid progress.

FINDINGS

On the part of the UN member states, a protocol for the regulation of Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems was presented at the CCW Convention on Prohibitions or Restrictions on the Use of Certain Conventional Weapons Which May Be Deemed to Be Excessively Injurious or to Have Indiscriminate Effects (2) by a group of countries (3) that share a history of internal and/or external conflicts and have long-term experience with prohibited weapons, for example, antipersonnel landmines.

The protocol concerns the Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems (LAWS) which presuppose the application of AI in war. In this context, the use of AI materializes in the concept of “autonomy” from man and in executing a set of bellicose and strategic war actions, from selecting the targets to the application of force. The protocol addresses the “serious ethical, legal, humanitarian and security problems” imposed by these security systems and describes the concept of “autonomy” based on a series of war functions. It spells out what are the field actions that require “significant human control” including the maintenance of human management and in deciding the effective intervention on the use of force and in a series of specific situations including the attribution of responsibility and accountability.

The document proposes a ban on the entire production and logistics chain of LAWS that cannot ensure significant human control, including “those that operate in a way that cannot be predicted, explained, anticipated, understood or traced”. The contracting parties undertake to guarantee human supervision in LAWS in order to allow intervention and deactivation in all stages of an action; guarantee the action and information capacity of human beings to control the entire process, especially in restrictive and withdrawal actions; and finally commit to “instituting measures and mechanisms to prevent automation bias in system operations and to exclude such algorithmic biases, including gender and racial bias, in artificial intelligence capabilities invoked in connection with the use of a weapons system”.

The proposal innovates by asking member states to commit to transparency regarding the effects resulting from self-learning of the LAWS, in addition to encouraging other members with regard to the identification of such effects and the elaboration of good practices in the systematic review of the LAWS. We highlight the protocol's concern with mitigating the risks of weapons arising from new technologies, calling on member states to safeguard physical and non-physical security against cyber-attacks, counterfeiting, acquisition and piracy of such technologies by non-state actors, terrorist groups of any nature, as well as providing personnel training in order to prevent the illegal transfer of confidential information and protocol violations. And finally, it is of fundamental importance to bilaterally cooperate by using the UN legal instruments in case of disputes or divergences in the interpretations of the protocol, to meet once a year, to provide annual reports on its applicability and update.

CONCLUSIONS

The documents presented in this policy brief show, albeit asymmetrically, the evolution of reflections on AI and of the sector international regulations. According to experts, the idea of “AI Summer” is idealistic and would not be enough to solve the problem. The Letter does not raise the fundamental issue of the use of AI for weapons and does not consequently mention the risks that LAWS pose in terms of aggression to Human Rights. However, it assumes that such technologies have dimensions which are still unknown by the creators themselves. Moreover, it is understood that generative AI may come to acquire “autonomy” from human intelligence; that the use of such technologies has a profound impact on the current economic and social model; that international governance is needed for the development and application of AI, requiring the regulation, responsibility and accountability on the part of producers.

The international scientific community believe that the Letter could have been more specific. The document sounds like a bizarre *mea culpa* or a warning that induces more doubt than action, from a sector that has used and abused the freedoms of the virtual world to expand business on a global scale, breaks the rules of national markets and redefines the rules of the labor market, not to mention the fiscal disengagement of the virtual market, the lack of transparency in the use and sale of users' private data, and so on.

And what is most serious, according to our analysis, is the fact that the Letter ignores the LAWS as the most aggressive dimension of the “AI Era”, given its own nature of domination, leaving the reader adrift on the absence of ethical and moral parameters necessary for the creation, development and programming of the algorithms of these tools. Following the logic of global liberalism, the Charter assigns to the states the responsibility of supervising and financing the governance of AI. It is intuited that the damage generated by the extreme freedom that the IT sector has always enjoyed must be mitigated by global governmental action, suggesting in passing that Big Techs must also be held accountable. The Bigs Techs were protagonists in the generation of an environment of deregulation of social institutions from cyberspace.

The protocol presented at the CCW, in turn, demonstrates a proposal by some Member States regarding the more lethal use of AI: on the one hand, it proposes an effective regulation of LAWS autonomy, on the other hand, it categorically defines the opposite concept, that is, what is the “significant human control” over such weapons, without neglecting responsibilities, accountability, mitigation of effects, the unknown property of systems self-learning and, finally, control in the development of new emerging war technologies. Aware of the fact that the countries that signed the protocol come from the global south, who have experienced the disastrous effects of certain lethal weapons in their own territories and have suffered, or are still suffering, the effects of authoritarian governments and violations of Human Rights, social inequalities and ethnic, religious and gender conflicts – which in many cases are sources of migratory movements and vulnerable populations – the protocol represents an important starting point for other member states to formulate their proposals against the use of LAWS.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, we suggest some measures on the subject:

1. Artificial Intelligence must be developed for a culture of peace between countries. The documents converge on the need to establish ethical and moral parameters for AI to be a tool for human development. In the name of this commitment, all social actors involved, Big Techs and independent laboratories, governments, the scientific community and multidisciplinary groups, must draw up international protocols and certifications whose starting point is the prohibition of Lethal Autonomous Weapon Systems;
2. Stop research into generative Artificial Intelligence with neural networks indefinitely;
3. The documents point the way to regulatory solutions on the use of AIs, whether in the field of virtual tools available to the general population, or in terms of military weapons. Both point to solutions concerning the control of autonomy, self-learning, foreseen and unforeseen uses, danger of information and technology misuse and algorithmic programming;
4. Strengthen the role of humans in the process of training the programmers and AI laboratory personnel on any type of operation that creates, develops and updates tools in the AI sector, on the legal and responsible use of emerging technologies and on the ethical and moral limits provided for by the international legislation in force and/or to be laid down by international organizations;
5. Certification of prior and mandatory virtual tools before the launch of the networked software according to established parameters, as well as international UN regulations;
6. Reinforce the social responsibility of Big Techs and IT laboratories, since they recognize the socio-economic impacts of technology. Force IT laboratories to establish strategies to mitigate side effects in their tools. Impose the requirement to establish digital inclusion and development strategies on countries lacking in technologies.

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